

TRAGEDY, SELFHOOD, AND NARRATIVE ETHICS: REVISITING JULIAN BARNES' 'THE SENSE OF AN ENDING' VIA JAGANNATHAN'S REFLECTIONS

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Abstract

This paper will look at the philosophical and literary aspects of Julian Barnes' novel 'The Sense of an Ending' by using the critical aspects of the essay 'On Making Sense of Oneself' by Dhananjay Jagannathan. The study concentrates on the complex interanimation of memory and identity, narrative ethics as well as rewriting classical tragedy in a postmodern setting. Relying on a variety of theoretical approaches, such as the philosophy of memory presented by Paul Ricoeur, the response to ethical criticism of certain points as explained by Martha Nussbaum and the virtue ethics propagated by Alasdair MacIntyre, the paper traces how the retrospection of the main character Tony Webster illustrates the shifting nature of self-narration and the problematic clarity of morals in the context of scattered memories.

The study through qualitative analysis and interpretive inquiry focuses on the pivotal role that non-reliable narration and post-hoc sense-making play in developing personal identity. This novel has been presented as a contemporary tragedy and not one with any great falling though with a lingering and unchecked sense of moral ambivalence and lost remembrance. As the findings suggest, the novel by Barnes overturns the hierarchical understanding of guilt, responsibility, and resolution bringing about a more fluid and unstable self, which is endlessly required to negotiate its past. Finally, the paper has shown that 'The Sense of an Ending' makes major contributions in terms of philosophical literature in regard to issues of self-understanding and morality of recollection in modern literature.

INTRODUCTION

Julian Barnes's 'The Sense of an Ending' (2011), winner of the Man Booker Prize, is a haunting narrative exploring the unreliability of memory, the illusion of self-awareness, and the elusiveness of truth in the recollection of one's past. It is the retrospective narrative of Tony Webster, who appears to be a typical Englishman, and tries to recreate and recall the events of his youthful years to discover that he was too wrong about the details of his memories

and the vision of his character was uncomplete. Although the novel has already been approached by a great number of critical readings, including the examination of its genre structure, psychoanalytical as well as ethical aspects, the 2013 article "On Making Sense of Oneself: Reflections on Julian Barnes' The Sense of an Ending" by Dhananjay Jagannathan deserves particular attention as one of

the most philosophical and unique reactions to the novel.

The article presented by Jagannathan is not only dealing with the unreliable memory of Tony or his attempts to escape the responsibility. Rather, it reads the novel in the context of Greek moral philosophy, that is in the context of its views of tragedy, moral agency, and aspiration. The main argument of this critique by Jagannathan is that the tragedy of Tony is not the classical loss or sorrow, but his inability to provide the meaning to himself- the failure of philosophical and ethical thought. With such a keen reinterpretation, this is not a moral depraved character in Tony but a man who has neither aspired into a jester of life, a big surprise, and not a classic tragedy.

This paper is an attempt to interpret and critically evaluate the article by Jagannathan as an important contribution to the academic designation to 'The Sense of an Ending', and regarding the issue of modern tragedy in the novel, the philosophical conceptual conflict between destiny and choice and the philosophical need to comprehend self-knowledge. Discussing how literary criticism and ethical philosophy go hand in hand, this paper attempts to examine how the very idea of memory, identity and personal development are questioned in the novel by Barnes.

1.1 Background of the Study

Over the past ten years, 'The Sense of an Ending' has become a topic of concentrated academic attention because of its fractured narrative form and the way it addresses issues of memory, guilt and the boundary between self-knowledge and self-delusion. Many critical analyses have focused on the novel's unreliable first-person narrator, its psychological ambiguity, and the ethics of personal history (Head, 2017; Ma & Lin, 2020). Nonetheless, the novel is rarely evaluated by philosophical critics using the theory of virtue ethics and Greek tragedy that allow viewing the moral consequences of the character and decisions of Tony in more detail.

Jagannathan's essay introduces this fresh perspective by interpreting Tony's passivity and lack of moral accountability as a form of modern existential failure, contrasting sharply with classical tragic heroes who suffer as a result of conscious decisions

and identifiable flaws (Aristotle, trans. 1996). Greek morals of ethics state that a human person gains his moral growth by consistent and responsible reflection and reflections of his own actions- something that Tony does not seem to do. The relevance of Aristotle's concept of hamartia, or a fatal flaw, is emphasized as a tool to understand what Tony lacks: aspiration, responsibility, and an honest reckoning with the past (Nussbaum, 2001).

Furthermore, Barnes's allusion to Frank Kermode's seminal work *The Sense of an Ending* (1967) further underscores the novel's philosophical ambitions. Kermode further suggests that people seek to bring semantically-predetermined narrative to the situation of chaotic reality, which Barnes (on the example of Tony trying to make sense of the messiness in his past and, as a consequence, of his present and future) is criticizing. The interpretation of Jagannathan, therefore, goes to the point of connecting literary form, theory of ethics and then character development (in the context) of how Barnes in effect reinvents tragedy as not grand death, but as small and creeping failure.

1.2 Problem Statement

Even though 'The Sense of an Ending' has attracted much academic discourse, most criticism is based on their instability as a story teller, psychological repression by Tony, and the subjectivity of truth and memory. Nonetheless, such methods fail to give attention to the ethical and philosophical aspects of the character of Tony. Although the theme of memory and regret has been explored by most of the critics, not many people have discussed the moral inactivity and aimlessness that constitutes the worldview of Tony.

This disparity is unanimously filled in the article written by Dhananjay Jagannathan as he examines the inability of Tony to reach self-awareness as a form of classical Greek tragedy and moral philosophy. However, no scholarly treatment of the philosophical interpretation of Jagannathan and its further repercussions of comprehending nowadays construction of personality and tragic art happen. This paper attempts to address this gap by critically examining the argument of Jagannathan and its follow-ups in line with the story by Barnes.

1.3 Research Questions

1. In what ways can Dhananjay Jagannathan recast an idea of a tragedy in view of 'The Sense of an Ending'?
2. How does the difference between the ideas of making sense to oneself and making sense of oneself assist in the analysis of Tony Webster as a character?
3. What value does Jagannathan philosophical model add to research already present on the novel?
4. How does the inability of Tony Webster to find self-understanding signal the idea that the idea of identity, agency and personal development in the present seems to be some type of failure?

1.4 Research Objectives

- To examine the standpoint of Dhananjay Jagannathan in relation to the interpretation of 'The Sense of an Ending' by using Greek moral philosophy.
- To assess the theoretical model between making sense to oneself and making sense of one self.
- To evaluate the extent to which Jagannathan criticism of the novel enlarges or criticizes current literary criticism.
- To investigate the consequences of the absence of aspiration and self-insight in Tony Webster as modern existential tragedy.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research is valuable to the scholars of literature and philosophy minded readers since it provides an interdisciplinary approach to the study of 'The Sense of an Ending'. The earlier criticism has pointed out to memory, history and narration as the important criticizing points, and in this study, we shall see the ethical and existential presence in the text as Jagannathan points out. The study has attempted to place the novel written by Barnes in the context of Greek tragedy and moral development and thus makes a broader overall picture of Tony Webster as an unreliable narrator but as a moral creature who has failed to achieve self-insight.

Additionally, the article by Jagannathan makes literature studies more interesting due to such focus

on aspiration as one of the forces of morality which the modern fiction has not been addressing with much attention. His study invites thinking about how literature may shed light on a practical problem like passivity, existential stagnation, and refusal of moral responsibility. In this way, the purpose of this work is not only providing the review of separate criticism work but also adds to the general discussions of the connection of literature and ethics as well as identity formation.

2. Literature Review

Julian Barnes's 'The Sense of an Ending' (2011) has been widely acknowledged as a modern psychological and philosophical novel that foregrounds the instability of memory, the fluidity of truth, and the construction of selfhood. The novel has remained a source of great academic interest across various fields such as literature, philosophy, psychology among others since its publication. Critics have explored a variety of themes, such as unreliable narration, ethical ambiguity, historical revisionism, and psychoanalytic interpretations of trauma and guilt (Groes, 2011; Head, 2017; Zamorano Llena, 2012). But very few have put the novel in the moral-philosophical prism Dhananjay Jagannathan uses in his article 'On Making Sense of Oneself'. The critical approach towards the usage of the existing literature on the novel is that in this literature review, the map of the study done on memory, identity, and tragedy by scholars will be brought out, and the essay by Jagannathan will be placed as a radical philosophical intervention that redefines the tragic in the modern piece of fiction.

2.1 Memory and the Fragility of Recollection

One of the biggest threads of scholarly discourse within 'The Sense of an Ending' is the finer point of memory as fallible and untrustworthy. The novel by Barnes is built on the basis of a first-person narration which resembles the inaccurate nature of the remembering. As Tony Webster admits early on, "what you end up remembering isn't always the same as what you have witnessed" (Barnes, 2011, p. 3). Such a recognition establishes the mood of a tale boasted with retroactive distortions and repressed memories. Critics such as Zamorano Llena (2012) and Groes (2011) observe that the novel challenges

the idea of memory as a reliable foundation for identity, a notion echoed in contemporary memory studies (Assmann, 2010; Ricoeur, 2004).

Groes (2011) argues that Barnes deliberately constructs a narrative in which memory serves not as a mirror of the past but as a mechanism of self-deception. This idea aligns with Ricoeur's (2004) proposition in *Memory, History, Forgetting* that memory is always interpretative and thus open to manipulation. Similarly, Whitehead (2009) explores how trauma reshapes memory and narrative, suggesting that traumatic events are often repressed, fragmented, or altered in one's recollection—a phenomenon clearly seen in Tony's inability to recall the full content of his hurtful letter to Adrian.

Although most of these scholars approach the issue of memory as the theme of the novel, Jagannathan goes an extra mile. He does not reject the importance of memory but he redefines the topic and says that, true issue is not forgetting as such but the inability of the protagonist to philosophically look into his own past and acquire moral self-recognition. Or, otherwise formulated, memory is not simply distorted, but it is not a processed morality.

2.2 Narrative Unreliability and Self-Deception

Unreliable narration, as a theme, is very deep-rooted in 'The Sense of an Ending', and critical analysts have come at the subject in different perspectives. Phelan (2007) and Nünning (2005) highlight how the unreliable narrator is often used in contemporary fiction to explore the limits of subjective truth. Being a narrator, Tony Webster is unreliable not in form of intentional deception, but on the basis of selective memory and rationalization. Genette's theory of focalization (1980) also becomes relevant here, as Tony's limited internal focalization skews the reader's understanding of events.

Herman (2009) links unreliable narration to broader cognitive narratology, arguing that first-person narrators like Tony create an illusion of psychological transparency while concealing essential truths. Such tension between illusion and truth leads to the core of how Tony constructs his identity, in which he unintentionally crafts a life story in which he has a way out of the guilt and responsibility. As Ma and Lin (2020) suggest, Tony embodies the ethical risks of narrating the self through "beautified

retrospection," gradually numbing himself to the real implications of his actions.

So, the difference with the reading of Jagannathan is that Jagannathan does not simply criticize the construction of a Tony story as it is, he pays attention to the philosophical consequences of this construction. The novel trick does not consist in the suggestion that Tony is withholding the truth to the reader but that Tony is withholding the truth to himself, more can be referred to as epistemic self-ignorance as opposed to narrative unreliability. This detail enables Jagannathan to add some more depth to the critique of the character, trying to explore all the ethical collapse at the roots of self-narration.

2.3 Tragedy Reimagined: From Sublime to Mundane

Tragedy as a concept has had its share of coverage in the field of literature using Aristotelian ethics. According to Aristotle's *Poetics*, a tragic hero is typically of noble stature and suffers downfall due to a hamartia—an internal flaw such as hubris, jealousy, or indecisiveness (Aristotle, trans. 1996). Scholars such as Nussbaum (2001) and Golden (1973) emphasize that tragedy, in the classical sense, is rooted in human agency rather than divine determinism. Tony Webster on the contrary, seems to be a man who does not make the moral decision, but allows life to occur to him without reflecting and making the serious action.

In *The Fragility of Goodness*, Nussbaum (2001) notes that the ethical life requires a balance between aspiration and acceptance of fate. Jagannathan adopts a similar approach by juxtaposing Tony with tragic figures like Sophocles' Heracles or Shakespeare's Macbeth, who, despite their flaws, make choices that lead to their downfall. Tony does not have such options, nor does he have such a philosophy of life; hence his knowledge as a tragic hero. There is no sublimity in the suffering of Tony, on the contrary, there is banality (Jagannathan). The tragedy itself is in not wanting to aspire and to transform or be confronted by the self in a truthful manner.

Furthermore, reconfiguration of tragedy on the part of Barnes fits postmodern mistrust of great narratives. As Hutcheon (1989) argues, postmodern fiction often dismantles traditional forms and genres,

replacing them with irony, fragmentation, and ambiguity. Instead of catharsis or redemption, the story of Tony concludes by means of the dead and unstructured cycle of thought: There is great unrest. This is why Jagannathan reviews the novel in terms of this postmodern tragic legacy, once sublime, now banal, and the novel must be seen as a kind of downward mobility, the fall into banality, not the fall into sin.

2.4 Ethics, Aspiration, and Self-Knowledge

The novel by Barnes also engages itself in bigger philosophical discussions of moral responsibility, self-consciousness, and aspiration. Taking a leaf out of virtue ethics (specifically Aristotelian and neo-Aristotelian approaches), Jagannathan argues that the life of Tony is an ethical failure since it is devoid of aspiration. Aspiration, as discussed by Callard (2018), is not merely about achieving goals but about the transformative project of becoming a better person. Tony does not move to participate in this project and stays hesitating and stagnating in his thought.

Further, in making this distinction between, on the one hand making sense to oneself, and, on the other hand, making sense of oneself, Jagannathan relies on philosophical investigations of narrative identity. Ricoeur (1992) argues in *Oneself as Another* that selfhood is constructed through reflective storytelling that integrates past actions into a coherent ethical narrative. Tony fails this test. The fact that he cannot place his past actions into a context of responsibility clouds him ethically to everyone, including himself.

Additionally, thinkers like Charles Taylor (1989) and Alasdair MacIntyre (1984) emphasize that moral identity is shaped through a dialogical process with the community. Tony is, nonetheless, a highly individualist and solipsistic character, who is opposed to the intersubjective aspects of moral development. His relationships with Veronica, his daughter Susie and even his ex-wife Margaret are marked by a kind of affectlessness and ethical avoidance. Jagannathan is correct in detecting this as the actual lapse of moral motive by the personality.

2.5 Conclusion

The academic criticism of 'The Sense of an Ending' has been intense and varied including the issues of

memory, reliability of narrative, and moral ambiguity. Most of these readings do not go so far as to deal with philosophical aspects of the novel, however. The article written by Dhananjay Jagannathan provides an interesting intervention, as he talks about the novel and its author in terms of classical and contemporary morality. His interpretation of Tony Webster not as someone under the punishment of fate, but under the punishment of a lack of aspiration and moral reflection is very welcome contribution to criticism of Barnes.

Jagannathan helps to create a redefinition and provides a new definition of what exactly a modern tragedy is given how they have the novel aligned to the ideas of Greek tragedy and virtue ethics. His clarity with regard to various types of self-understanding as well as his focus on aspiration, responsibility and ethical selfhood allow reading the text in a more developed and critical way. His work therefore forms the background of the future interdisciplinary studies aiming at linking together the literary studies and the moral philosophy.

3. Methodology

In this section, the research methodology in order to analyze the philosophical reading of Dhananjay Jagannathan of Julian Barnes 'The Sense of an Ending' is described. The study is more qualitative and interpretative in its character; therefore, it uses a critical-analytical approach as applied in literary hermeneutics and philosophical discourse study. The purpose is to evaluate the quality of projection and novelty of the argument provided by Jagannathan and put it in the context of larger literary and philosophical research. This chapter shows the design of the research, the arguments on methodological selection, data collection procedure, analytical framework, and ethical ambiguities in this research design.

3.1 Research Design

This study will be qualitative and interpretative in design, which is the most appropriate to the study of literary texts and philosophical arguments. The most appropriate typology would be critical literature review and conceptual analysis, where one reads an article of Jagannathan closely and her article

establishes an intertextual connection with *The Sense of an Ending* and is backed with secondary scholarly sources.

The design is non-empirical, it neither contains field-based collection of data, like survey or interviews. Rather, it indulges in a text interpretation exploring elaborate concepts of memory, tragedy, self-awareness and moral responsibility. This method is perfect in answering the research questions indicated in the study since these questions focus on abstract notions and literary ethics.

3.2 Methodological Approach

The study uses two core methodological approaches:

3.2.1 Philosophical Literary Criticism

This approach draws upon the intersection of literature and philosophy to interpret texts through ethical, metaphysical, and epistemological frameworks (Nussbaum, 1990; Culler, 2011). Jagannathan's reading of Barnes is deeply embedded in Aristotelian ethics and the theory of tragedy, particularly as it relates to hamartia (tragic flaw), agency, and aspiration. By applying the tools of philosophical reasoning to literary interpretation, this research assesses whether Jagannathan's thesis offers a convincing moral critique of Tony Webster's character.

3.2.2 Intertextual and Thematic Analysis

Intertextuality enables the researcher to follow theme and conceptual relations between texts. Barnes's novel explicitly references Frank Kermode's *The Sense of an Ending* (1967), and Jagannathan's essay implicitly dialogues with philosophical works by Aristotle and modern theorists such as Bernard Williams and Alasdair MacIntyre. The thematic analysis focuses on recurring concepts such as memory, responsibility, tragedy, and moral aspiration, enabling the study to draw meaningful parallels across texts and interpretations (Allen, 2011).

3.3 Data Collection

The primary text under examination is:

- Jagannathan, D. (2013). "On Making Sense of Oneself: Reflections on Julian Barnes' *The Sense of the Ending*". *The Point Magazine*.

- The secondary sources include:
- The novel *'The Sense of an Ending'* by Julian Barnes (2011).
- Relevant philosophical texts: Aristotle's *Poetics* (trans. Heath, 1996), Martha Nussbaum's *The Fragility of Goodness* (2001), and Bernard Williams's *Truth and Truthfulness* (2002).
- Literary criticism and journal articles focused on the novel, character studies, unreliable narration, and ethical reading (Head, 2017; Ma & Lin, 2020; Jordan, 2015).

Relevant scholarly materials were found using academic databases including JSTOR, Project MUSE, Google Scholar and Cambridge Core. All articles and books were peer-reviewed and used in the final data so that the validity and scientific approach were suitable.

3.4 Data Analysis

The study employs critical discourse analysis (CDA) as a tool to deconstruct the philosophical and literary language used in Jagannathan's article. The analysis proceeds in several stages:

3.4.1 Close Reading

The initial phase demands a careful close reading of the article by Jagannathan in order to distinguish the main claims, the structure of reasoning, and the philosophy implemented. The textual evidence is annotated to highlight moments of conceptual insight and logical coherence (Leitch, 2010).

3.4.2 Conceptual Mapping

With the help of a conceptual map, it is possible to trace the appearance of the key philosophical terms in Jagannathan article: such terms as aspiration, tragedy, self-understanding, moral agency are revealed and referred back to the novel. The correspondence or discrepancy between the novel and the interpretation is registered.

3.4.3 Comparative Interpretation

The statements of the article get contrasted with other critical reflections on *The Sense of an Ending* particularly those that concentrate on memory, regret, and usual narrators. By means of such a comparative framework, the researcher is able to evaluate to what extent Jagannathan has contributed

something new to the sphere and whether his contribution is strong or not.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The present article is based on the uses of publicly available sources of texts and the secondary literature; thus, it implies no impact on human participants and no ethical risks. However, ethical considerations in literary research require proper citation, fair representation of the author's views, and avoidance of plagiarism. Academic integrity has been observed by citing all sources according to the APA guidelines of 7th edition.

3.6 Limitations of the Methodology

Although this approach of critical-analysis would suit in the studies of philosophy and literature levels, there are several drawbacks to it:

- Subjectivity is inherent in interpretative methodologies. The same texts may have different conclusions to their different readers.
- It is only restricted to studying one article and one novel, which might be a hindrance as far as generalizations to other literary context are concerned.
- There is no availability of empirical backlash of the readers or critics, who would have increased more layers to the interpretation.

Nevertheless, even in these limitations, the methodology gives a powerful and systematic way to discuss the relationship between philosophy and literature in the reading of Jagannathan of Barnes.

3.7 Conclusion

This section has expounded the methodological decision employed in carrying out a critical and philosophical review on Dhananjay Jagannathan on his interpretation of 'The Sense of an Ending'. With the help of close reading activity, thematic and intertextual analysis, philosophic reasoning this research will provide a critical assessment of the re-invention of the idea of modern tragedy in the novel by Barnes. In the following chapter, the detailed results and discussion of the findings using this methodology will be given.

4.1 Discussion

This section will present an in-depth analysis of the critical essay by Dhananjay Jagannathan titled 'On Making Sense of Oneself' as applied to 'The Sense of an Ending' by Julian Barnes. It is the exploration of how Jagannathan re-cites the novel in a philosophical way, especially by relying on Aristotelian ethics and the idea of tragedy. The discussion takes into account the merits and possible weaknesses of this reading as it locates the reading in the grand scheme of things of literary and philosophical inquiry. These are some of the important themes addressed by the novel: fallibility of memory, the definition of self-consciousness, whether we can aspire to be moral, how the novel handles contemporary existential quandaries.

4.1 Jagannathan's Argument: A Philosophical Reading of Tragedy

The main point of Jagannathan is that 'The Sense of an Ending' is to be considered as a psychological novel first about memory and regrets and then as a modern tragedy in the Aristotelian sense. He posits that Tony Webster, the protagonist, embodies a form of hamartia—not through a fatal flaw in the traditional sense, but through moral complacency and a failure of aspiration (Jagannathan, 2013). This recontextualizes Tony's actions, or inactions, as more than just personal failures—they become emblematic of the modern individual's retreat from responsibility and self-confrontation.

Aristotle's notion of tragedy involves the fall of a character due to an error in judgment rather than sheer vice (Heath, 1996). The passive avoidance that makes up the course of the narrative of Tony befits this model surprisingly well. Instead of the epic failure, the tragedy is in the fact that he does not want to achieve anything more—not to have a better moral life or to confront what he has done.

Jagannathan's emphasis on aspiration as a moral project aligns with recent philosophical work by Agnes Callard (2018), who distinguishes aspiration from mere ambition or desire. The tragedy of Tony is that he did not aspire, rather than he tried and did not get what he wanted. This interpretation shifts the critical focus from memory as a narrative device to memory as a moral faculty, echoing similar themes in Nussbaum's (2001) *The Fragility of Goodness*.

4.2 Memory, Narrative, and the Ethics of Recollection

According to Jagannathan, Tony turns out to be an unreliable narrator not because it is a literary form, but because of his moral psychology—his desire to remodel past events to absolve himself, since he does not agree with it. This claim resonates with Bernard Williams's (2002) concept of "truthfulness," where genuine self-understanding depends on the will to confront uncomfortable truths.

The novel by Barnes focuses on the incompleteness of memory, a remedy which can be better seen in the fragmentation and circularity of the memory of Tony. Being sure that his memory is perfect, Tony starts to tell the story that later falters due to new discoveries. Jagannathan is keen in analyzing this narrative pattern as an ethical dilemma: how can one define himself or herself when his past is either distorted, withheld, or conveniently forgotten?

This moral interpretation is not only psychological one since one wants to know whether he/she is responsible to have incomplete or selective memory. As Head (2017) notes, Tony's greatest failure is not forgetting but refusing to revisit the past with moral seriousness. This nuance is well brought out by Jagannathan who presents the novel as a case study in evaded responsibility.

4.3 Modern Tragedy and the Ordinary Life

Among the most provocative statements by Jagannathan can be counted his prescription that 'The Sense of an Ending' is a tragedy of the commonplace. In contrast to the classical tragic stories about rulers and warriors, the novel written by Barnes revolves around the life of a retired middle-class Englishman who dwelt on being guarded and passive.

This is a reading that asks us to address conventional ideas about the tragic hero and propose a new figure, the tragedy of ethical minimalism. It is not Tony that failed at evil, but he failed at living an ethical life, at making a choice between comfort and confrontation, safety, and self-improvement. As Jordan (2015) remarks, Tony's self-image is dangerously sanitized; he sees himself as a passive observer, not a moral agent.

By aligning this with Aristotle's idea of anagnorisis (recognition), Jagannathan repositions Tony's late

self-realization as a kind of tragic awakening—but one that comes too late to redeem the past. The sadness of the novel, therefore, lies not in dramatic loss but in missed moral opportunities (Culler, 2011).

4.4 The Role of Veronica and Secondary Characters

The essay by Jagannathan concentrates primarily on Tony, yet his interpretation raises matters concerning the character of Veronica Ford, the female opposite pole that is enigmatic and badly misunderstood. Veronica is transformed as a reflecting glass to the limits of Tony and constantly reminds him that, You just don't get it, do you? The refrain can be repeated citing the main difficulty of the novel, the divide between recollection and conception.

From a feminist literary perspective, Veronica can also be read as a symbol of repressed truth—a woman burdened with emotional labor and concealed trauma, which Tony consistently fails to see (Ma & Lin, 2020). This is avoided in Jagannathan's essay, though his notion of moral aspiration may get enlarged to include the ways in which the gendered habit of interpreting oneself conditions the relation to self and moral development.

Adrian, another pivotal character, also represents a moral counterpoint. Tony makes his naive assessment of causality and guilt hard to challenge by the fact that this philosophical genius committed suicide. Jagannathan suggests this, yet a further examination of Adrian's epistemic courage, his readiness to believe the painful truth, would still have contributed to the tragic aspect of this story.

4.5 Critique and Evaluation of Jagannathan's Reading

The reading offered by Jagannathan is interpretively strong, rich in philosophy, who brings in a fresh ethical sobriety to the approach of reading contemporary fictions. However, some critiques can be made:

- His focus on aspiration and tragedy sometimes overshadows the novel's postmodern qualities, such as its metafictional structure and narrative unreliability (Leitch, 2010).
- To better even out the moral-philosophical perspective of the essay, it could use a

broader exploration of other understandings to the text, such as post-structuralist, psychoanalytic or feminist critique.

- As much as the Aristotelian lens throws light on it, it narrows down the range of reading that may fail to capture the criticism of modern existential alienation as depicted by Barnes.
- Nonetheless, the main idea of Jagannathan which consists in the fact that this novel presents a tragedy of not heroism, but mediocre ethical people is new and convincing.

4.6 Synthesis with Existing Literature

Jagannathan's interpretation stands in dialogue with a growing body of criticism that reads 'The Sense of an Ending' through ethical and philosophical lenses (Head, 2017; Nussbaum, 2001; Williams, 2002). His essay is a contribution toward this discourse because it presents a moral typology of the contemporary anti-hero: the tragic feature of this type of hero is non-excess, but rather lack of achievement.

Moreover, by reframing Tony's "sense of an ending" as a failure to construct a morally coherent self, Jagannathan aligns with the existential concern of how one can live meaningfully in a fragmented, postmodern world (Allen, 2011).

4.7 Conclusion

In this section, the critical analysis of the reading of 'The Sense of an Ending' by Jagannathan has been described, indicating the strengths, philosophical insight and its limitations. That Aristotelian formulation was able to re-conceive the novel as a contemporary tragedy of moral complacency. Through the employment of the themes like aspiration, memory, and recognition Jagannathan can contribute to the themes of both literary and philosophical discourse handsome. The final and last chapter will conclude the most important findings, implications of this reading and the prospective of future studies.

5.1 Conclusion

This article has been a critical review of the essay titled "On Making Sense of Oneself: Reflection on Julian Barnes' The Sense of an Ending" by

Dhananjay Jagannathan. The essay attempts to discuss how philosophical interpretations especially those based on the Aristotelian ethics and ethics psychology related to philosophies may help to shed more light on contemporary literary works. In the understanding of Jagannathan, the novel of Julian Barnes is placed into the framework of a contemporary tragedy not in a collective sense of elevated action and tragic fault, but a personal one, based on mediocrity of ethics and moral passivity and not to strive.

In the course of the thesis, it has been seen that the emphasis put by Jagannathan on the idea of aspiration an idea of philosopher such as Agnes Callard serves as a lucrative analogy within the scope of which we can analyze the character of the protagonist, Tony Webster. Both the passive way in which Tony steers himself through life, his selective memory, and his hesitant, belated recognition of the importance of moral responsibility all add credence to what Jagannathan states: the novel is a tragedy of the commonplace, a tale in which a moral downfall is precisely the unwillingness of the main character to seek further moral development.

The paper has used this philosophical perspective to illuminate some of the central themes that become interlaced throughout the novel and have shown the epistemic vulnerability of memory, the grounding complexities of self-realitation, the ethical burden of the memory, the development of regret as moral understanding. In addition, the gendered aspects of these dynamics, especially the aspect of Tony misinterpreting Veronica, were also explored and how Barnes, the author, condemns the self defensive stories we adopt to abscond our mistake.

The main question that Jagannathan poses in his essay and that is used as the central question of this work is what it means to make sense of oneself. Barnes' novel does not make it simple to find answers: it provides fragmented reminiscences, half-conversations and ominous realization that it can be too late to reconcile. However, in turning this into tragedy Jagannathan recaptures the narrative as not only cynical or postmodern, but as ethical and emotionally tense. Such moral richness, which is typically absent in postmodern fiction, makes the novel endure various philosophical dimensions.

5.2 Contributions of the Study

This article contains the following contributions to literary and philosophical scholarship:

- It brings Jagannathan's philosophical interpretation into dialogue with wider ethical theory, especially the concepts of aspiration (Callard, 2018), recognition (Aristotle, 1996), and truthfulness in memory (Williams, 2002).
- It provides a reclamation of the modern tragedy so that it does not emphasize heroic failure but ethical laziness and unseized chances.
- It helps to explain 'The Sense of an Ending' as a novel that does not only discuss the unreliability of the memory but also the unethical result of evading the self-examination.
- It prepares the convenience to accommodate feminist and psychoanalysis approach in the context of philosophical-moral perspective, especially with the help of the analyses of Veronica and Adrian.

In so doing, the present research article reaffirms the worth of interdisciplinary literary criticism in which the philosophical knowledge complements the literary knowledge and the latter knowledge complements the former.

5.3 Limitations of the Study

Although the analysis provided in the study is rather thorough in its assessment of the essay by Jagannathan and the underlying philosophy presented therein, there are limitations involved:

- The analysis focused heavily on a single interpretation (Jagannathan's), leaving out more extensive engagement with other critical lenses such as post-structuralism, reader-response theory, or trauma studies.
- The place of secondary characters- namely Veronica and Adrian, was to be considered, but not represent the same philosophical complexity in terms of time and theme basis since the attention was on the character of Tony Webster and his moral journey.
- The research is largely theoretical and interpretive. They did not include empirical

data, including study of reader reception, or more textual comparisons.

The gaps can be addressed in future research by broadening the horizon of its interpretation and examining other works of contemporary fiction through the philosophical prism of Jagannathan.

5.4 Recommendations for Future Research

It can be suggested on the basis of the study findings and limitations that the future study be directed to the following directions:

1. Applications: If the Jagannathan redefinition of tragedy were adopted, how might it be applied to other postmodern or contemporary novels with protagonists whose ethical stance is ambivalent, novels like *Ian McEwan, Atonement or Kazuo Ishiguro, The Remains of the Day?*
2. Feminist Ethical Readings: Explore the ethical dimensions of female characters in *The Sense of an Ending*, particularly Veronica, using feminist moral philosophy (e.g., Held, 2006) and trauma theory.
3. Memory as Moral Narrative: Compare the matter of memory and moral responsibility in literature, through such texts as Barnes, Proust, Sebald, etc.
4. Empirical Reader Response Studies: Explore by qualitative interviews or survey the answers to seeing what different readers perceive about the ending of the novel and the moral responsibility of Tony Webster.
5. Pedagogy Applied across the Curriculum: Teaching and learning ethics and literature in the higher education curriculum with the case study 'The Sense of an Ending', to encourage the valuation of reflective discussions about memory, morality, and the narrative self.

5.5 Final Reflections

In sumamry, by approaching 'The Sense of an Ending' within the philosophical framework of Jagannathan, the novel becomes an incredibly compelling state of reflection on moral apathy and the problem of self-knowledge. In a world frequently characterized by cynicism, coolness, and emotional

distance, the subdued melancholy and moral challenge of this novel work on a very humane level. Such a reading by Dhananjay Jagannathan is not a mere critical intervention, but it is an invitation. A challenge to a reconsideration of what constitutes tragedy in contemporary life. In order to appreciate that ethical failure is not always accompanied by a disaster. And that sometimes the saddest stories are the ones where just nothing much happens- except the gradual realization that life could have been lived and done in a different and meaningful way, had only it been brave enough to attempt it.

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